

TE | SF

Transforming Education
for Sustainable Futures

CALL TO ACTION

Climate and
Environmental
Justice Education

JULY 2023

THE CHALLENGE

“climate and environmental degradation issues are here, **they are real**, AND they impact on the most marginalised first, ... **education systems are very slow to respond**”

“Areas that were once tree-covered rangelands are now treeless plains” ... “Somaliland entered its fifth failed rainy season” ... “Schools were flooded” ... “People remain alienated from their land” ...

Transformative education responses across all levels and forms of education are needed.

Co-created research across the TESF Network shows that environmental degradation and climate change are not distant issues to be learned about some time in the future. They are here, they are real, and they are impacting on the most marginalised communities directly, affecting their livelihoods, ways of being and their futures.

Environmental degradation and pollution impacts are caused by unsustainable development patterns. This negatively affects people’s livelihoods, health and quality of life. It impacts the lives and livelihoods of the most marginalised, ecosystems, biodiversity, water and food systems. Current laws and governance are not arresting environmental degradation and its impacts. Centralised approaches fail to advance sustainability at local levels. Improved livelihoods, food and water security, climate action, and well-being of people and planet are impacted. Education systems are too slow to respond.

Transformative education must strengthen citizen engagement and action for environmental and climate justice.

WHAT NEEDS TO BE TAKEN SERIOUSLY

... evidence informed
recommendations for
transformative
education that **advance
climate and
environmental justice**

Everyone should be involved:

Formal, non formal and informal education processes in and across schools, community education programmes, universities, and Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVETs) are all needed for co-creating environment and climate change justice in collaborative, participatory ways.

For example:

In **Rwanda** the 'One Child One Tree' programme linked communities and schools in climate action, creating 'children forests' that promoted social harmony and tackled climate change. In **South Africa** museums, universities and schools co-operated with social movements on reframing sustainability education. In **Somalia**, a TVET programme led to changes in basic services for local communities improving local sustainable development, while an eco-school project addressed water, health and climate change challenges in the school.

In **Rwanda** eco-school projects supported integration of climate change and sustainable development within the competency-based curriculum, while farmers who have been dealing with climate variability for decades were able to share their knowledge to increase the adaptive capacity of the community. In **India** projects gave special attention to listening to marginalised voices, including children's, showing how this led to new knowledge and understandings about the environment, climate change, citizenship and intergenerational inequality.

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Education should be multi-modal, embrace plurality, and be inter- and transdisciplinary:

Climate and Environmental Justice education is not just about learning climate science, it should start in place and context, engage peoples' matters of concern, be ethics-led, relevant, integral to all curricula and learning programmes, and include Indigenous knowledge and critical, creative practices in ways that advance actionable knowledge and agency for transformative, sustainable futures.

For example:

In **South Africa**, the 'Lore of the Land' photography project surfaced unacknowledged relations to land, reframing modernist and colonial law curricula. Also in **South Africa**, residents in the City of Cape Town instituted a community water mapping co-learning activity to strengthen water activism and agency to claim rights to water.

In **India** multi-modal and interdisciplinary learning took place in 'water classrooms' and in a Carbon Summer School. In India, eco-schools programmes modelled holistic education practices that democratised decision making. School gardens and water education in **India, South Africa, Rwanda and Somalia** all offered places for exploring practical ecology, principles of sustainability, care and solidarity building in integrated ways.

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Active, transformative, transgressive and experiential learning is needed:

Learning approaches are needed with power to contribute to agency for transforming the unsustainable status quo, addressing the immediacy of issues (e.g. early warning for droughts and floods), and co-creation of alternatives in critical, creative and inclusive ways.

For example:

Across **South Africa, India, Rwanda, and Somalia** school and community food gardens were developed that strengthened teachers, children, school leaders and community members and leaders agency to advance food security and resilience to droughts. In **South Africa**, communities engaged with power structures, challenging decisions on mining, water management and affecting their lives without their participation.

In **Somalia** schools collaborated with communities using action learning and indigenous methods. In **Rwanda**, during the creation of school gardens, more positive outcomes were observed when children also created home food gardens.

In **South Africa, India, Rwanda and Somalia** showed the importance of grounding quality education in children's lived experiences, connecting their knowledge(s) of the world and environment with engagement with new knowledges and experiences.

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Education should be systemically minded, expansive and regenerative:

Education needs to include and foster expanded repertoires, practices, knowledge(s), languages (including Indigenous knowledges and languages) and support systemic strategies in mitigating, adapting, building climate resilience and creating regenerative, transformative alternatives for more sustainable futures.

For example:

In **South Africa** youth engaged in a translanguaging project to develop indigenous vocabularies in response to climate change challenges. Coastal communities engaged in empathetic community building and solidarity-based activism to address degradation of their livelihoods through mining. In **Rwanda** an educational project supported building climate hazard resilience. In **Somalia**, the meaning, possibility and relevance of the circular economy in the context of the Horn of Africa was articulated, and educational materials in local languages contributed to climate change education in schools.

In Rwanda use of Kinyarwanda allowed teachers to contribute freely to community engaged projects and vice versa, and in **India** a textbook analysis project showed up the narrow ways in which conservation is portrayed, excluding the complex and multi-dimensional relations that Adivasi communities have with nature - spiritual, cultural, philosophical as well as material.

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Education should be transgressive of unsustainable norms:

Climate and Environmental Justice education should explicitly advance alternatives to unsustainable norms, engaged curricula, forms of empowerment, and human activities that are more sustainable, inclusive, and decolonial in construction. It should be open-ended and accommodate what is not yet known.

For example:

In Rwanda, India **and** South Africa arts-based methods were used to challenge unsustainable norms in various ways, building understanding and engagement with climate and environmental justice concerns.

In **India**, Adivasi communities constantly threatened by dispossession, reclaiming ecocentric interconnected understandings of life, that have been disrupted by colonial modernity, in the process re-interpreting ecological sustenance and social relationships. In **Rwanda** eco-schools projects were initiated to develop sustainable practices in schools with surrounding communities.

In **South Africa** a community cooking project addressed sustainable food system patterns at community level. In **Somalia** nomadic pastoralists collaborated with researchers to improve livestock management in response to drought conditions and climate change.

CALL TO ACTION

What we ALL need to do TOGETHER ...

***EVERYONE has a role to play in co-creating education for sustainable futures for ALL living on our planet ...
What role are you [can you] playing?***

Transformative Environment and Climate Justice Education is needed across education and learning systems.

Such education should champion approaches that are inclusive of diversities of ecological and social relationships. For this, the foundations of colonially inherited education systems need to be fundamentally transformed.

A call to action:

- **For Researchers:** Undertake co-engaged educational research that crosses traditional education sector boundaries, and that engages transdisciplinary, transformative approaches; explicitly addressing environment and climate justice concerns.
- **For Educators and Teachers:** Develop curricula and pedagogical practices that are inclusive, critical, creative and transformatively engaged, that develop agency for transformative change.
- **For Policy Actors:** Critically review the colonially inherited foundations of education and transform education systems to be more relevant and responsive to people's needs, and the well being of people and the planet. Give much more attention to how policies 'come alive' at local levels.
- **For Engaged Activists:** Support community empowerment and agency for change and raise the profile and impact of climate and environmental justice in community learning networks, forums and media, and strengthen links between communities and educational institutions for innovation.

THANK YOU!!

visit: <https://tesf.network/>

This CALL TO ACTION, compiled by Heila Lotz-Sisitka with Amal Ali, Poonam Batra and Michael Tusiime is based on the findings of 67 co-engaged research projects implemented across 4 countries in the Transforming Education for Sustainable Futures Network involving India, Rwanda, South Africa and Somalia/Somaliland. Overall co-ordination was supported by the University of Bristol and partners, with UKRI with GCRF funding. It was complemented by substantive in-kind support and collegial relations that contributed significantly to the project's outcomes and success through intellectual, social, economic, ethical and other contributions.

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